

Effect of C-based soil conditioners on the composition and properties of soil organic matter

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Biochar is a carbon-containing product of the thermal decomposition of organic raw materials under conditions of limited oxygen access and is widely regarded as a sustainable soil conditioner capable of improving the physical and chemical characteristics of agroecosystems [1]. One of the key areas of research into its impact is its effect on the chemical properties of soils, including humic substance content. Humic substances are natural high-molecular organic compounds formed as a result of the transformation of plant and microbial residues in the soil. They form the basis of humus and play a key role in soil fertility.

The aim of the study was to investigate the effect of two types of biochar, separately and in combination with a humic preparation, on the chemical properties of sod-podzolic soil in a series of model experiments and to identify their potential as soil conditioners.

The application of soil conditioners contributed to an increase in the carbon and nitrogen content of the soil. In the control, the carbon content was 1.42%, with the addition of biochar from siderites – 2.02%, biochar from coffee – 2.22%, potassium humate – 1.8%. Total nitrogen also increased, with the maximum value (0.17%) observed when using biochar from coffee.

Water-soluble carbon in the control was 186.1 mg/kg. The highest values were recorded when potassium humate was applied (379.9 mg/kg), while biochar exhibited sorption properties, reducing or retaining mobile forms. A similar pattern was observed for nitrogen: in the control — 46.94 mg/kg, with the addition of potassium humate — 57.66 mg/kg, with biochar from coffee — 49.41 mg/kg, with biochar from green manure — a decrease to 44.28 mg/kg.

Alkali-hydrolysable forms also increased significantly with the addition of potassium humate (carbon — up to 3917.0 mg/kg, nitrogen — up to 286.2 mg/kg). Mixtures of biochar with humate showed intermediate values, indicating the sorption capacity of biochar and the leading role of humate as a source of humic substances.

The total C content increases by 0.4-0.8% in accordance with the amount of organic soil conditioners added. Neither biochar affects the size of the mobile pool C in both aqueous and alkaline extracts, whereas humate, separately and in mixture with biochar, increases the proportion of mobile fractions of soil organic matter from 10 to 20-30% to total C. Under the conditions of this experiment, the organic matter of biochar did not transform and remained in the non-hydrolysable part of humus.

In the applicative phytotest on wheat seedlings, biomass growth of the test culture was detected only in the variants with biochar from coffee and humate, amounting to 4-9% compared to the control, but the differences are not significant. A decrease in biomass was observed in the variants with the addition of biochar from green manure and a mixture of coffee biochar with humate (up to 62-75% compared to the control, statistically insignificant) and a mixture of green manure biochar with humate (up to 65% compared to the control, statistically significant).

Reference

1. Weber, Kathrin, and Peter Quicker. "Properties of biochar." *Fuel* 217 (2018): 240-261.